

STRATEGIC CHANGE MANAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF MINISTRY OF HEALTH IN NAIROBI CITY COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract: Despite several attempts to improve service delivery, the Kenyan Ministry of Health remains inefficient due to a lack of effective strategic change management. The Ministry of Health's performance in Nairobi City County, Kenya is affected by strategic change management. This research sought to analyze that impact. Social network theory, human capital theory, and resource-based views served as the study's guiding theoretical frameworks. A descriptive survey was research tool used in this study. 159 medical practitioners working in NCC, Kenya, focused of the research, which was conducted by the Ministry of Health. In order to choose the respondents, a basic random sampling procedure was used. A total of eighty individuals made the sample. The utilization of surveys allows for the collection of first-hand information. Thirteen questionnaires were sent to individuals working in the Ministry of Health within the Government of Machakos County as part of the pilot study. This is the reason why the researcher had to choose the Ministry of Health in Machakos County. When it comes to qualitative data, content analysis was used for analysis, and narratives was used for presentation. Quantitative data, including standard deviation and mean, were included in the descriptive analysis, which was shown in tables and figures. To further understand the interplay between the variables, the researcher used multiple regressions. The research discovered a positive and statistically significant relationship between performance and continuous improvement. Spending on employee education and growth is directly proportional to a company's bottom line. Results showed that improved unit communication did not affect organizational performance. Technology adoption significantly affected organizational performance, according to regression coefficients. Continuous improvement improves performance by eliminating inefficiencies, simplifying processes, and using resources more efficiently. Employees need training and development to improve their knowledge, skills, and competences, which lead to the company's success. Communication is vital to an organization's dynamics, yet it may not have had the greatest impact on the performance outcomes considered. For stakeholder satisfaction, modern organizations must continually adjust every department to increase performance. Other data suggest that modern businesses should continually modify all parts to succeed. The research advises the Ministry of Health to assess its communication channels, methodologies, and technology for strengths, weaknesses, and gaps.

Keywords: Communication, Continuous improvement, Performance, Strategic change management, Technology adoption, Training and development.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Olajide (2018) states that several factors, such as changes in technology, product and service offerings, and client preferences, contribute to the high level of competition in Nigeria. This is why experts in change management have devised a plethora of methods for gauging an organization's preparedness for transformation and why this process is so crucial. Because in today's cutthroat and ever-evolving economic climate, every company's survival depends on its

capacity to implement and execute effective change management strategies. The capacity of a firm to adjust and prosper in the current dynamic and uncertain economic environment depends on the proficiency of its leadership in handling change (Dibella, 2019).

Parastatals in Kenya have reportedly been running and handling change recently (Ndunge, 2019). Organizations have changed in response to changes in business interaction methods, which has led to reorganization inside business units with the goal of enhancing overall performance. Furthermore, according to Bayo and Harcourt (2020), the management of change in these parastatals has been confronted with a variety of problems, which the organization might create means of overcoming or minimizing. As a result, it can be argued that organizational management makes successful strategic changes, but they may fail in the transition phase.

1.1.1 Strategic change management

Quesada-Pineda and Madrigal (2016) define continuous improvement as incremental process and product enhancements that save money and boost productivity. Continuous improvement improves processes, goods, and services throughout time. Atkinson (2017) states that continuous improvement is a steady process that seeks minute incremental changes in accordance with change management. Continuous improvement also aims to improve corporate processes to boost productivity and cut costs, according to Otieno (2016). Thus, for continuous improvement to work, all employees must be involved and the company must have a learning culture. This study analyzed continuous improvement based on cost reduction, staff involvement, and learning culture.

Training and development programs help employees enhance their skills and knowledge to better serve their employers (Nda & Fard, 2015). According to Jehanzeb and Bashir (2018), companies with a complete training and development strategy retain more employees, boost profitability, and have a more engaged workforce. Additionally, it helps the organization minimize the expenditures of losing skilled staff. Change management requires training. Employees need timely, relevant training to adjust and develop flexible skills. This research assessed training and development based on participant empowerment, skill improvement, and knowledge gain.

Effective communication has long been acknowledged to transform organisations (Kitchen and Daly, 2016). It helps with change preparedness, ambiguity reduction, and communication-based commitment. Jabri, Adrian, and Boje (2018) recommend mentioning the training in communications about the change and change management plan. Certain people dislike change, thus communicators should try to reduce its stress. Training information gives confidence. Thus, successful change management programs require well-planned and managed communications. Communication indicators include change awareness, preparedness, and acceptance.

Technology adoption involves recognizing and using new technologies to increase production and profit. Irwin, Hoffman, and Geiger (2018) say it minimizes resistance, enhances communication, and addresses key change difficulties. Ullah, Iqbal, and Shams (2020) state that modern organizations manage more than people, customers, and stuff. Given the current state of digital transformation, many modern organizations must be able to adapt to change to survive. Thus, effective technology change management requires constant improvement. This study will measure technology adoption using service automation, technical support, and digital workplaces.

1.1.2 Performance

One definition of performance offered by Ricardo et al. (2017) is the extent to which an organization can achieve its stated goals and objectives via the efficient and wise use of its resources. The ability of an organization to make the most of its strengths, fix its weaknesses, and grasp opportunities while avoiding risks is called organizational performance (Richard, Devinney, Yip, & Johnson, 2019). This competency is essential for every business that wishes to realize its goals. The opposite is true according to Njoroge (2019), who said that there is no optimal way to evaluate the success of an organization. This is due to the fact that various businesses have varied objectives and objectives, which therefore need different methods of measuring their achievements.

The extent to which organizations achieved their goals is referred to as performance (Georgopoulos & Tannenbaum, 2017). Lebens and Euske (2018) state that performance assessments have expanded to include non-financial and financial metrics that reveal how far down the path to success the path has gone. However, HR management, service and product quality, brand awareness, and company success are all examples of non-financial analytics. Profitability, income, ROI,

and cash flows are some of the financial analytics. Consequently, this study will include operational efficiency, service quality, service accessibility, and innovation as performance indicators.

1.1.3 Ministry of Health Department in Nairobi City County

The duties of the Ministry of Health have been defined by the government in Executive Order No. 2 from May 2013. The Ministerial Strategic and Investment Plan has significant importance within the country's planning process. The Constitution, Kenya Vision 2030, and the second Medium Term Plan 2013–2017 are its primary sources. After then, it is passed down via the 2017–2022, Strategic and Investment Plan for the Kenyan Health Sector. In addition to serving as the foundation for yearly planning and performance contracting, this plan will also serve as a reference for the planning and budgeting.

The health care delivery system in NCC is composed of five tiers, with levels 1 through 5 being controlled by the National Commission for Health. These tiers are responsible for providing Kenya essential package for health services to the different cohorts. Nairobi's population is served by more than 500 institutions, including 121 community units that are fully operational, which are located inside the county. Here is a rundown of the current available facilities: 106 institutions owned by the state sector, 132 by religious and non-profit groups, and 271 by private companies. In accordance with the Nairobi County Integrated Development Plan 2018-2022, level 5 refers to county referral institutions that are connected to the national referral system situated at level 6.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Schedule Four (2010) of the Kenyan Constitution requires the NCC Government to provide equal healthcare to all citizens. This group includes cemeteries, pharmacies, ambulance services, food licensing and regulation, trash dump administration, and solid waste disposal (Constitution of Kenya, 2010). Kenya's health system has a referral plan with standards and criteria, according to the Ministry of Health Kenya (2012). This will assist the sector build an effective health system for the public. Global, regional, and local issues limit human capital and health despite millions of dollars in investment in the health industry. The Nairobi County Integrated Development Plan 2018–2022 recognizes health sector problems. Due to the unequal distribution of human resources and the lack of different health sector capabilities, providing efficient services has been difficult. Health care access, utilization, and funding discrepancies have caused administration inefficiencies. Due to new and reemerging health challenges and changing social behavior, new health dangers and non-communicable diseases have emerged, straining the county's health care infrastructure.

Maboko (2012) found that the Kenyan Ministry of Finance did not provide enough resources to help managers alter the organization, which hurts employee performance and strategic change management. This research is contextually irrelevant because it was undertaken at the NCC Ministry of Finance, not the Health Ministry. Edward and Muturi (2016) found that strategic organization techniques affect transformation in Kenyan government ministries. Ministry architecture should be adaptive, and staff should be encouraged to participate in programs. Nyaguthii (2016) found that an under empowered workforce hinders change management at the Kenya Trade Network Agency. Organizational effectiveness and regulatory changes in Kenya's agriculture and livestock research organization were investigated by Osege (2018). A statistically significant although minor positive relationship was found. This research seeks to fill various conceptual and contextual gaps noted in previous investigations. This study sought to understand how strategic change management assists the Kenyan Ministry of Health in NCC.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The primary aim of this research was examining the impact of strategic change management on the performance of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

Research was conducted with these specific objectives:

- i. To investigate the impact that continuous improvement has on the performance of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya.
- ii. To investigate the extent to which training and development have an impact on the performance of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya.

- iii. To investigate the extent to which communication has an impact on the efficiency of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya.
- iv. To investigate the impact that the use and acceptance of technology has on the functioning of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya.

1.4 Research Questions

These research questions formed the basis of the study:

- i. How does continuous improvement impact the performance of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya?
- ii. How does training and development influence performance of ministry of health in NCC, Kenya?
- iii. To what extent does communication influence performance of ministry of health in NCC, Kenya?
- iv. How does the implementation of technology impact the performance of the Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Resource Based View Theory

Selznick (1957) and Penrose (1959) developed the RBV Theory, which emphasized internal resources as a key competitive advantage. Wernerfelt (1984) and Barney (1991) advanced RBT theory. RBT advocates believe that finding, obtaining, and using rare, precious, and exclusive resources that other companies lack or can't match is the key to organizational success. RBV views the firm as an assembly of resources, with different resources playing diverse roles in value development, according to Wernerfelt (1984). Employee expertise and experience and product and service branding are intangible assets for companies. To maintain a competitive edge, maximize your resources. Thus, its limited, irreplaceable, and incomparable resources give the organization a competitive edge that allows it to execute well. Firms have intangible strategic resources.

According to Barney (1991), the RBV theory emphasizes organizational compatibility with opportunities. Thus, the RBV mechanism maximizes firm resources to build key capabilities needed to gain and retain a competitive edge. Thus, firms must connect their internal skills to the external environment to achieve the competitive strategic position that improves performance. Training and ongoing improvement boost performance by improving internal capacities. It promotes training and development, continuous improvement, and performance variables, making it the main theory.

2.1.2 Human Capital Theory

This study was guided by Schultz's 1961 Human Capital Theory (HCT). HCT says a company's productivity might grow if its employees perform well. Human capital theory views employees as assets, not costs. Businesses use "human capital" to refer to their staff. Intelligence, talents, and understanding make this concept unique to the organization. The HCT emphasizes potential contributions to a firm as much as actual efforts. Boxall (1996) calls this "human capital advantage". Intangible assets include human capital, which is not owned by the employer. Companies benefit from training and getting to know their people by establishing learning corporate cultures or teamwork vocabularies. This is true even when human capital is not legally owned.

This is relevant to the investigation since human capital is considered crucial to boosting an organization's assets. Thus, good human resource management is necessary to attract and retain top talent, enhance productivity, and weather global competition. The concept is based on the idea that training and development boosts organizational performance and worker productivity.

2.1.3 Social Network Theory

Scott's (1991) Social Network Theory underpinned this study. Scott says that social network theory explains the web of relationships around every person, organization, or institution. This method studies social relationships using a network of nodes and linkages. Nodes are the actors in the networks, while ties are their links. Social network theory is strong because individual attributes are less essential than how they interact and are associated with other network members, according to Scott (1991). This approach differs from sociological research. Thus, personal networks greatly impact success.

Haythornthwaite (1996) suggests regular information exchange for social networks. These networks' nodes are actors, and their connections are information-transmission interactions. The information exchange connection determines how people in this social network share and receive information. According to Haythornthwaite (1996), information exchange relationships reveal the types, receivers, and amounts of information sharing. As network nodes, people may encounter particular forms of data. Network data exchange patterns reveal how information flows across a system and how actors position themselves to help or hinder it.

The SNT studies an organization's communication network, which includes internal communication. Organizational communication patterns—formal and informal—are considered. According to Haythornthwaite (1996), these communication patterns can explain certain organizational phenomena. For instance, workers' connections in the communication network affect the information they see and can influence. According to the notion, employees communicate via these networks, which may help bring about company-wide change. The communication variable supports the idea.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Continuous Improvement and Performance

The effect of commercial banks in Kenya using techniques for continuous improvement on their efficiency was the subject of Otieno (2016)'s study. The research used an exploratory descriptive survey strategy to gather qualitative data. Recipients of the piece were 39 commercial bank branch managers. A questionnaire served as the main instrument for gathering data in this investigation. Results showed that continuous improvement techniques like customer focus, staff involvement, quality improvement programs, effective leadership, and data-driven decision-making were positively correlated with business efficiency. Previous research, which focused on the banking business, offers contextual differences to the present study, which will concentrate on the health sector. In order to fill the methodological vacuum, the study will be built on quantitative data.

2.2.2 Training and Development on Performance

A study was carried out by Weru, Iravo, and Sakwa (2013) to assess the correlation between state-owned firms' performance and training and development. An explanatory research approach was used in this work. A total of 142 participants were chosen from among 232 human resource managers who were the intended subjects of the research. For this study, a questionnaire was used. The first step in exploring the relationships between the variables was to compute the correlation coefficients. The data shows that training and development programs are associated with more successful organizations. Nevertheless, this examination will use a descriptive strategy, in contrast to that study's explanatory research style.

2.2.3 Communication and Performance

Wang (2019) set out to study how different types of communication affect the success of initiatives aimed at increasing employees' loyalty to their employer. The study's overarching goal was to dissect the nature of the connection between Chinese organizational commitment, job-related communication, and personal, emotional, and social-affective communication. For the purpose of the research, a statistical method was used to examine the survey data. There were up to 69 individuals from a Chinese local government agency that were part in the investigation. Regression analyses indicated that top-down and bottom-up social-emotional communication was a positive predictor of emotional investment, perceived organizational strategic understanding, and vertical involvement with management. Furthermore, both emotional and normative commitment are strongly predicted by work-oriented communication. It was from these results that the regression analyses were extrapolated. The present inquiry, on the other hand, will focus on the Nairobi City County, Kenya Ministry of Health, even if the research was carried out in China. No background information is provided. Filling a conceptual gap between previous studies that focused on the significance of communication in boosting employees' organizational commitment, the present investigation will concentrate on the connection between communication and productivity.

2.2.4 Technology Adoption and Performance

Technology alignment and the success of Kenyan manufacturing companies was the subject of Chege's (2019) investigation. Information gathered from a self-administered survey was analyzed utilizing a quantitative research strategy for an explanatory study. Technology had a major impact on the efficiency of the 240 organizations that were tested,

according to the data. The study's conclusions suggest that companies should put money into research and development of new technologies and methods that boost company performance. The analysis focused on industrial enterprises, however, so there's a contextual gap there. Kenya will serve as the setting for this investigation, with an emphasis on the NCC Ministry of Health.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher (2021)

The factors under consideration in Figure 2.1 include continual improvement, training and development, communication, and technology adoption. The variable under investigation is the organizational performance. The indicators of organizational performance is operational efficiency, access to services and quality service and innovation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study used a descriptive survey methodology as its chosen research strategy. This research technique helped the study as it leads to the collection of a lot of data and makes it possible to get detailed information, whether it's quantitative or qualitative.

The Ministry of Health in NCC, Kenya, was the focal point of study, with a total of 159 management officials (at various levels) employed in the ministry's divisions, including lower, middle, and top positions. Healthcare facilities, medical services, public health initiatives, and departments focused on wellness and nutrition. This being a census study, there were no sampling done.

A standard random selection approach was used to choose the participants in the study. The study had a sample size of 159 individuals, based on the total number of participants. A sample size of eighty persons was included.

The primary information was gathered via distributing questionnaires to the individuals who took part in the study. The questionnaire had two sections, which were as follows: In Section A, demographic information was supplied, and in Sections B, C, and E, readers provided information that were more focused to fulfilling the goals of the research. According to the Likert scale, there are five possible responses: 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (undecided), 4 (agree), and 5 (strongly agree). This made it possible to quantify the viewpoints.

A combination of quantitative and qualitative elements was included in the dataset. The research used narrative presentation and theme analysis to go through the qualitative data. When looking at numerical data, descriptive statistics like the standard deviation and mean were used. A tabular and graphical depiction of the results of this study were provided. This study used SPSS version 20.0 for its statistical analysis. To further determine the relative importance of each variable, the research used inferential statistics such as multiple regressions and correlation analysis. Here we lay out the procedure for creating the regression equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Whereby

- Y = Performance
- X₁ = Continuous improvement
- X₂ = Training and development
- X₃ = Communication
- X₄ = Technology adoption
- β₁ to β₄ = Coefficients
- ε = error term

4. DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

4.1.1 Continuous Improvement

The respondents were requested to state the level of agreement on how continual improvement affects the health ministry's performance in NCC, Kenya. The results are presented in Table 1 below

Table 1: Continuous Improvement

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
As a result of the organization's commitment to minimizing waste, continuous improvement results in more effective planning for the group.	3.788	0.1232
A decrease in expenses and an increase in income are the two primary drivers of increasing profitability, which are achieved via continuous development.	4.732	0.966
The perception that they are required to be inventive and creative in order to find solutions to issues and enhance company procedures is one of the factors that contributes to increased employee motivation.	3.992	1.123
By making everyone aware of what the organization is striving to accomplish and their part in attaining the company's plan, continuous improvement helps to develop a strong communication system across the whole organization.	4.422	0.777
Through the implementation of continuous improvement, the Ministry is able to consistently concentrate on the appropriate priorities, enhance performance, and preserve its competitive edge in the market.	3.898	1.332
All levels of the company have a solid understanding of the notion of continuous improvement.	3.999	1.121
Average Mean	4.138	0.907

Source: Survey data, 2024

With an average score of 3.788 and a S.D of 0.1232, participants unanimously agreed that good organizational planning is the result of continual development. This is because of the company's commitment to reducing waste. A large majority of the participants (M=4.732, S.D of 0.966) agreed that cutting expenses and raising revenues via continuous improvement results in better profitability. The majority of the participants agreed with this. With an average score of 3.992 and a S.D of 1.123, it's clear that continuous improvement encourages employees to think outside the box when solving problems and improving business processes. Worker enthusiasm is boosted by this conviction. A large majority of

respondents (M=3.992, S.D 1.121) agreed that employees are more motivated by a culture of continuous improvement because they are led to think that they must utilize their imagination and creativity to address problems and improve business operations. The study found that the Ministry can continuously focus on the right priorities with continual progress (M=3.898, S.D=1.352). Upon reviewing the data, it became clear that the concept of continuous improvement is successfully communicated across the whole company. This was shown by a high Mean score of 3.999 and a S.D of 1.121. A cumulative mean of 4.138 and a S.D of 0.907 were found.

Respondents were given free-form instructions to describe the impact on the organization's output of the Ministry's continuous performance improvement initiatives. It was found out that by continuously analyzing and refining processes, the ministry can eliminate redundancies and streamline workflows, leading to faster service delivery and reduced operational costs. Continuous improvement allows the ministry to better allocate resources (time, money, personnel) to areas where they are most needed, ensuring more effective use of public funds.

4.1.2 Training and Development

The respondents were requested to state the level of agreement on how training and development affects the health ministry's performance in NCC, Kenya. The results are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Training and Development

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
In addition to introducing workers to leadership abilities and software expertise that they will need in the future, training and development programs assist employees master the skills that are necessary for them to perform their present positions.	4.675	1.112
Through participation in employee training and development programs, workers are able to remain current on changes that have occurred within the Ministry, such as those pertaining to ethics, safety, or quality standards.	3.998	1.235
Training and development provide workers with the ability to adjust to working remotely and contribute to the seamless transition of having to make this adjustment.	4.345	0.991
Training and development programs are designed to assist workers in enhancing their existing strengths and addressing any flaws that have been noted in their performance reports.	4.567	0.994
The soft skills that are needed for adjusting to changes in the workplace and in society are strengthened via employee training and development programs.	3.897	0.777
Average Mean	4.296	1.0218

Source: Survey data, 2024

Table 2 shows that most people think that development and training programs help employees learn new skills (mean = 4.675, S.D = 1.112). Researchers found that staff members who participate in training and development programs are better able to adapt to new circumstances (M = 3.998, S.D = 1.235). (M=4.345, S.D =0.991) The results demonstrated beyond a reasonable doubt that employees are able to adapt to remote work and aid in the smooth transition when given opportunity for training and development. It was clear from the training and development programs' findings (M=4.567, S.D=0.994) that these programs help employees improve upon their strengths and fix the weaknesses identified in their performance reviews. (M=3.897, std Dev=0.777) The findings demonstrated that employee training and development programs are effective in enhancing the soft skills that are particularly important when it comes to responding to changes in the workplace and in society. There was a S.D of 1.0218 and an average mean of 4.296. The participants were asked to provide their responses to an open-ended question that inquired about the impact that the Ministry's training development initiatives are having on the organization's overall performance. Employees are able to gain new skills and information that are pertinent to their positions via the use of training programs, as was discovered. Workers are better able to manage their obligations in an efficient and effective manner as a result of this, which leads to enhanced work performance. According to the results, the Ministry of Health often promotes peer learning as a means of educating employees on how to deal with change efforts via its training and development programs.

4.1.3 Communication

The respondents were requested to state the level of agreement on how communication affects the health ministry's performance in NCC, Kenya. The results are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Communication

Statement	Mean	Std. Dev
The personnel are informed and clarified about how to enhance their performance and how to continue with the changes that are planned to take place inside the ministry via communication, which in turn fosters motivation.	3.334	0.852
For the purpose of identifying and evaluating several potential courses of action, communication serves as a source of information.	4.414	1.015
A key component in shaping employees' perspectives on effective change management is the capacity for clear and concise communication.	3.997	1.224
Good communication helps foster good relationships between the Ministry's senior management employees and the lower level employees	4.761	1.200
Good communication helps to build a positive work environment within the ministry	4.668	1.111
Average Mean	4.235	0.7778

Source: Survey data, 2024

Communication has shown to be effective in fostering motivation among workers by providing them with information and clarification on how to continue with the changes that are meant to take place within the ministry as well as how to enhance their performance (M= 3.334, S.D=0.852). The outcome also show that communication is a source of information to help identify and assess alternative course of actions (M=4.414, S.D =1.015). The results in Table 4.8 expressed that good communication helps foster good relationships between the Ministry's senior management employees and the lower level employees (M=4.761, S.D= 1.200). Good communication helps foster good relationships between the Ministry's senior management employees and the lower-level employees (M = 4.761, S.D= 1.200). Good communication helps to build a positive work environment within the ministry (M=4.668, S.D=1.111). The average mean was 4.235 and S.D of 0.7778. On the open-ended questions, it was found out that clear communication ensures that all employees understand the ministry's goals, objectives, and priorities. When everyone is on the same page, efforts are better aligned, leading to more efficient and coordinated actions towards achieving the ministry's mission. According to the findings, the process of consultation is an ongoing process that occurs throughout the whole of the process of introducing and implementing change.

4.1.4 Technology Adoption

The respondents were requested to state the level of agreement on how technology adoption affects the health ministry's performance in NCC, Kenya. The results are presented in Table 4 below

Table 4: Technology Adoption

Statement	Mean	Std. Dev
Technology assists the Ministry with managing changes to operations	4.710	0.999
The ministry works to link its computer systems with those of their customers and suppliers by taking use of the advancements that have been made in communications technology.	4.887	1.202
The ministry is able to remove redundancy and even outsource certain administrative duties thanks to the use of automation.	4.659	0.995
Through the use of a centralized user interface, the deployment of technology enables scalability across the Ministry, especially in distant locations.	4.888	.770
Employees are able to work flexible hours and connect to people and information whenever, wherever, and on whatever device they want thanks to the digital workplace.	4.833	0.889
Average Mean	4.795	0.971

Source: Survey data, 2024

The results indicated that technology provides the Ministry with a significant amount of assistance in managing changes to operations. The mean score for this assistance was 4.710, and the S.D was 0.999. The majority of respondents (M=4.887, S.D=1.202) were in complete agreement that the ministry makes use of the advancements that have been made in communications technology in order to link their computer systems with those of their customers and suppliers. In addition, the results demonstrated that the ministry is able to minimize redundancy and even outsource some administrative duties thanks to the use of automation (M=4.659, Std Dev=0.995). The implementation of technology enables scalability throughout the Ministry, even distant locations, via the use of a common interface, as shown by a mean score of 4.888 in table 4.9. To add insult to injury, the digital workplace gives workers the ability to work flexible hours and interact with people and information whenever, wherever, and on whatever device they want (M=4.833, Std Dev=0.889). The average mean was 4.795 and S.D of 0.971. In an open question it was stated that technology adoption allows the ministry to automate routine tasks and processes, reducing manual work and increasing operational efficiency. This leads to faster service delivery and frees up staff to focus on more strategic tasks. In general, the findings revealed that Technology adoption allows the ministry to automate routine tasks and processes, reducing manual work and increasing operational efficiency. This leads to faster service delivery and frees up staff to focus on more strategic tasks.

4.2 Performance

Results from an examination of the health ministry's performance in Nairobi City County were presented and discussed here. Table 5 illustrates the condensed findings.

Table 5: Performance

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Strategic change management enables the Ministry to improve its operational efficiency	3.86	.862
Strategic change management enables the Ministry to offer quality service	4.14	.724
Strategic change management through automation of processes in the City county helps to improve performance	4.05	.862
Strategic change management enables the Ministry to come up with unique services and products	3.79	1.091
Adoption of modern technology has enabled access to quality health care	3.79	.909
Stakeholders engagement/involvement in decision making helps to improve delivery of services in the health sector of Nairobi City County	3.54	1.078
The health care system in Kenya's Nairobi County benefits from ongoing education and training.	3.77	.991
Cumulative average	3.83	0.94

Source: Survey data, 2024

As indicated in table 5, the study found out that strategic change management enables the Ministry to improve its operational efficiency with a mean of 4.14. Strategic change management through automation of processes in the City county helps to improve performance had a mean of 4.05 and 3.86 respectively. Strategic change management enables the Ministry to come up with unique services and products and adoption of modern technology has enabled access to quality health care, both had a mean of 3.79. The health care system in Kenya's Nairobi County benefits from ongoing education and training had a mean of 3.77, while the question on, stakeholders' engagement/involvement in decision making helps to improve delivery of services in the health sector of NCC, had a mean of 3.54. The entire cumulative mean score for this part is 3.83, and the S.D is 0.94. Furthermore, the overall mean score is 3.83. This suggests that the respondents generally agreed that the institution's primary function was to carry out the health ministry's directives.

4.3 Regression Analysis Results

Multiple regression analysis was used in the research project in order to highlight the impacts of continuous improvement, training and development, communication, technology adoption, and performance. The results are shown in Table 6, which may be seen below.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.883 ^a	.780	.768	1.51607

a. Predictors: (Constant), continuous improvement, training and development, communication, technology adoption

Source: Field Data (2024)

A high positive link between the analyzed variables is shown by the model summary, which shows a correlation value of $R = 0.883$. A total of 76.8% of the variance in organizational performance was explained by strategic change management, with an adjusted R-squared value of .768. When it comes to organizational performance, however, other, unrelated variables will explain 23.2% of the variation.

Table 7: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.415	3.116		5.588	.000
1 continuous improvement (CI)	.724	.154	.305	4.717	.000
1 Training and Development (TD)	1.198	.134	.640	8.958	.000
1 Communication(C)	.155	.255	.096	.606	.547
1 Technology adoption (TA)	.672	.251	.403	2.676	.009

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings of the research reveal that four independent factors, namely continuous improvement (CI), training and development (TD), communication (C), and technology adoption (TA), had a substantial role in explaining the changes that occurred in the dependent variable. There is a significant difference ($\text{Sig} < 0.05$) in the organizational performance. The selected model, which may be seen below, included four independent variables;

$$P = 17.415 + 0.305 \text{ CI} + 0.640 \text{ TD} + 0.096 \text{ C} + 0.403 \text{ TA} + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

4.3.1 Test of continuous improvement on Organizational Performance

A description of the model's findings follows: An organization's performance is valued at 17.415 units according to the model, assuming all other parameters remain constant. Continuous improvement significantly impacts the company's success, according to statistical study ($\text{sig} = 0.000$). As a consequence of the unit variation in continuous improvement, the performance would fluctuate by 0.305 units.

4.3.2 Test of Training and development on Organizational Performance

The results of the coefficient of regression on the effect of training and development on organizational performance indicate a significant positive correlation ($\text{sig} = 0.000$ as the significance level). Alterations in training and development are responsible for considerable unit changes in organizational performance ($B = 0.640$), which amount to a substantial 0.640.

4.3.3 Test of Communication on Organizational Performance

According to the findings of the regression analysis on communication, the variable did not play a significant role in explaining the differences in organizational performance that occurred across units ($\text{sig} = 0.096 > 0.05$). Furthermore, the findings make it abundantly evident that the changes in communication between units did not play a substantial role in explaining the variations in organizational performance.

4.3.4 Test of Technology Adoption on Organizational Performance

The results of the regression coefficients demonstrated a significant correlation ($\text{sig}=0.001$) between the use of technology and the organization's performance. A one-unit shift in technology use is associated with a 0.403-unit shift in business performance, as seen in the results.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study results were that continuous improvement had a significant positive relationship on performance existed. In conclusion, Continuous improvement fosters the identification and elimination of inefficiencies, resulting in streamlined processes and better resource utilization, which directly boosts performance. By regularly assessing and refining practices, continuous improvement contributes to higher quality outcomes, whether in product quality, service delivery, or customer satisfaction.

There is a great deal of evidence from studies and real-world applications in many various fields that back up the study's conclusions that training and development significantly improve organizational performance. Training and development opportunities must be made available to employees so that they may enhance their knowledge, skills, and competencies; this will ultimately lead to the success of the organization. Organizations have the ability to achieve sustainable success, innovation, and a competitive edge in their market if they make investments in the continual development of their people.

In conclusion, the change in communication was found to be insignificant in explaining the changes in organizational performance. This suggests that while communication is an important aspect of organizational dynamics, it may not have been a key factor influencing the specific performance outcomes under consideration. Other variables, such as leadership, employee skills, or process improvements, may have played a more significant role in driving performance changes in this context.

Moving on to a different conclusion, modern corporations must regularly implement changes across the board to appease their stakeholders and boost organizational performance. Formulating a plan to manage change in a sustainable way and implementing technological innovations as an effective way of managing change are both crucial tasks in the quest of any long-term and permanent success. Given that consumers provide the bulk of a business's income, it stands to reason that customer preference management would boost operations across the board.

5.2 Recommendations of the Study

According to the findings of the research, the Ministry of Health should encourage staff at all levels to develop a mentality that is focused on always learning and improving. Training sessions, seminars, and the exchange of best practices may be held on a regular basis to accomplish this goal. The ministry should encourage employees to contribute ideas for improvement. Establish channels for employees to suggest improvements and recognize their contributions.

The study also recommends that the ministry to develop training programs with clear, measurable objectives that directly contribute to improving organizational performance and health outcomes. Implement specialized training programs for leaders and managers to enhance their skills in strategic planning, decision-making, and change management. Effective leadership is crucial for driving organizational performance.

The study recommends that ministry of health to evaluate current communication channels, processes, and tools to identify strengths, weaknesses, and gaps. This includes both formal and informal communication methods. Establish clear guidelines and policies for internal communication to ensure consistency and effectiveness.

Lastly the study recommend that organizations can optimize their technology adoption processes, leading to improved performance, increased efficiency, and a stronger competitive advantage. The ministry of health should foster a culture that encourages experimentation with new technologies and innovative approaches. Support initiatives that explore emerging technologies and their potential benefits.

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